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THE ROLE OF MUHAMMAD YUSUF'S CREATION IN FORMING A SENSE OF COMMITMENT TO REFORMS IN YOUTH

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Abstract: *In this article, an attempt was made to reveal the modern trends of using the power of literature, art and culture in forming a sense of belonging to reforms in the youth through the poetry of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Muhammad Yusuf.*

Key words: *Poetry, lyrical image, lyrical character, poetic fragment, poetic collection, creativity, life, talent, the concept of bravery, the period of reforms.*

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada yoshlarda islohatlarga daxldorlik tuyg'usini shakllantirishda adabiyot, san'at va madaniyatning kuchidan foydalanishning zamonaviy tendensiyalarini O'zbekiston xalq shoiri Muhammad Yusuf she'riyati orqali ochib berishga harakat qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *She'riyat, lirik tasvir, lirik qahramon, she'riy parcha, she'riy to'plam, ijod, hayot, iste'dod, dahldorlik tushunchasi, islohotlar davri.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье предпринята попытка раскрыть современные тенденции использования силы литературы, искусства и культуры в формировании чувства сопричастности к реформам у молодежи через поэзию Народного поэта Узбекистана Мухаммада Юсуфа.*

Ключевые слова: *Поэзия, лирический образ, лирический персонаж, поэтический фрагмент, поэтический сборник, творчество, жизнь, талант, понятие храбрости, период реформ.*

There are many poets who have expanded the pure sky of our beautiful language with their words. That is the happiness of Uzbeks. There is no feeling or concept that cannot be sung in this language today. The great Navoi showed the limits of those who considered the Turkish language to be rough and unfit for poetry in the 15th century. At the beginning of the 20th century, Qadiri and Cholpon surprised those who were concerned about the difficulty of writing a prose work in Uzbek with their unique word poetry in prose. Among the next generations, great poets, who are considered architects of the artistic word, grew up. So, the holy chain continues and will last as long as the nation stands. In the last quarter of the last century, the poet Muhammad Yusuf, who shined like a guiding star in the pure sky of our literature, came to the attention of people with his simple and sincere words and his unique poetry. In his short life, he was able to make a happy contribution to the rise of national poetry and modern singing. Erkin Vahidov wrote about the poet: "Muhammad Yusuf is loved and cherished by our people, he is honored as the singer of the Motherland, the singer of Independence, he appreciates and sings his tender, sincere poems, which are instilled with great love and loyalty to the Uzbek people. His poetry can truly be called winged poetry, poetry that flies high in the sky and gives wings to hearts."

He is an honest poet, an honest and pure soul. That is why his poetry is full of all spirituality, whether he sings about love, weaves a song about an unfaithful country or about our history and destiny, there is always a sense of harmony with life and reality. His poems are simple, smooth, and seem to be in harmony with folk oral creativity. "Muhammad Yusuf was a unique talent, kind, honest, brave and humble person..." said the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov.

Muhammad Yusuf, the beloved poet of our people, was born on April 26, 1954 in the village of Qovunchi, Marhamat district, Andijan region. He grew up as a lover of two sons and three daughters of father Yusuf and mother Enakhan. Muhammad Yusuf, the owner of a unique talent, was a lively young man in his childhood, interested in many things, love in his heart, the enthusiasm of the blood flowing in his veins is clearly reflected in his poems. Since childhood, Muhammad Yusuf was intelligent and

very curious, so he loved to read many books and searched for answers to questions. At the same time, Muhammad Yusuf was an open-minded and dreamy child, and he had a great love for Sharia and literature. His grandmother Tursunkhan had awakened such love in his heart. Although Muhammad Yusuf was born in an ordinary peasant family, he achieved great success in his studies and work. In 1973, he graduated from high school with excellent grades and entered the Reshetov Institute of Russian Language and Literature. Between 1978 and 1980, he served in the military, and these periods were a period of difficult and complex experiences for the poet, and the feeling of "Motherland" became even more intense in the poet's heart.

The work of the poet is poetry that calls for awakening. It is not poetry consisting only of personal experiences such as love, friendship, separation, and suffering. Poetry that invites the reader to live actively in social life, to be awake. One of his poems contains the following lines:

My sleepy tongue
I will tell you a secret.
God bless you
Pallada pulls.
Sleep - too
A life given to a nation,
As sleep increases
Your debt will also increase...

Every moment of life is measured, even sleep has a price. The reader who understands this sums up his life and is grateful to the poet.

Muhammad Yusuf's work is poetry glorifying universal human values. In his poems, connections to humanity, good qualities, all meritorious deeds are sung on the highest level. In a poem by Mansur, he says: "Every place where human ashes are placed is dear and holy. If that's the case, let people rub the soil of the grave on their eyes. Who is harmed by this. Here, the sanctity of a person, regardless of religion, belief, sect, race, nationality and color, and the sanctity of the soil on which his ashes

were placed, are glorified. The poet considers poetry and language to be a sacred heritage left by ancestors and must be passed down to generations. The purpose of teaching about Muhammad Yusuf should not be only to teach the life and work of a poet. At least, we should achieve that it consists of teaching to love the Motherland "without making claims" like Muhammad Yusuf, to teach to respect our mother tongue like Muhammad Yusuf without getting infected, and to teach to understand our incomparable national values like him.

In conclusion, I can say that everyone can sing about the motherland, but only an artist who can sing from the heart and who can celebrate the motherland can become a real poet! I think Muhammad Yusuf can be a bright example of this. Through his poems, the poet calls people to preserve our forgotten values and nation. The simple images in his poems, at the same time munificent and dear, their essence, i.e., the image of this motherland, sacred soil, the dignity and prestige of this homeland, are reflected.

Good memories have always been important to us. Muhammad Yusuf decorated his creativity with such a golden age that reading his poems, a person expresses great admiration for the joy, happiness and possibilities of imagination that he does not have. His place in Uzbek poetry is incomparable, and his literary heritage will be repeated for many years to come and will be remembered by everyone. Muhammad Yusuf's followers and admirers are inspired by his poems.

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